

**Photo physical, photodegradation and biological studies of synthesized
porphyrins (P1, P2) and metallo porphyrins (Pz1 Pz2)**

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Porphyrins and metalloporphyrins were formulated by linking phenothiazine and methoxy substituted phenyl ring and characterized by ¹H and ¹³C mass spectra. The photo physical properties have been investigated by UV –Vis absorption, steady state fluorescence spectroscopy and cyclic voltammetry measurements. The photocatalytic activity of these materials was evaluated by UV-Vis spectroscopy for the degradation of congo red under sunlight radiation. Antibacterial activities of the prepared samples were screened against Gram positive and Gram negative bacteria by measuring the zone of inhibition. Antioxidant activities were performed of porphyrins and metalloporphyrins for DPPH assay. In-vitro lung cancer (A549) activity of synthesized samples was carried out using MTT assay.

Keywords: Porphyrins, photo physical properties, antibacterial, antioxidant and anticancer activities.

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